
EUROSCITIZEN COST ACTION - WORKING GROUP INFORMAL EDUCATORS (WG3)

REPORT

Assessing in-person and online informal learning activities to promote understanding of evolution - a guide for practitioners

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Abstract

Informal learning activities are a powerful medium to promote understanding of evolution, as they have a wide reach. Although the diversity of the types of informal learning activities is large, a common issue is that learning outcomes are seldom assessed, and rarely a part of the activity design. In this report, we present the ethical considerations and theoretical perspective that can help practitioners adopt assessment as an integral element of the activity design. We also describe an exploratory study designing assessments to assess knowledge, engagement, motivation, utility and attitudes for two contemporary examples of in-person and online learning activities. We conclude by reflecting on our process and providing recommendations to encourage practitioners to improve their practice by incorporating assessments in their activities.

Keywords

Informal education, assessment, evolution education, ethics, assessment design, guide, online workshops, exhibitions, in-person learning, online learning

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INTRODUCTION

Informal learning complements the knowledge and skill base we all acquired during the formal schooling years. Given its availability and accessibility (through museums, zoos, science centres, nature trails, but also workshops, games and MOOCs), informal learning has a large reach and very diverse audience, and is therefore said to be life-Long, life-Wide, life-Deep (Banks et al., 2007). As such, all of these learning opportunities are an excellent medium through which poorly understood concepts, such as evolution can be reiterated and reinforced.

The EU COST Action EuroScitizen, aims to increase scientific literacy in evolution through a network of formal and informal educators, scientists, and science communicators. EuroScitizen's working group 3 (Informal education) previously established a need to encourage and facilitate informal educators and practitioners to include assessment of their activities as part of the activity design (Adnađević et al., 2020), especially when designing evolution-themed informal learning activities.

To guide our efforts, we use the definition of assessment as being “***the process of gathering and discussing information from multiple and diverse sources in order to develop a deep understanding of what students know, understand, and can do with their knowledge as a result of their educational experiences; the process culminates when assessment results are used to improve subsequent learning.***” (Huba & Freed, 2000)

Based on this working definition, and based on our previous findings (de Lima et al., 2023), the primary purpose of assessments is to improve participants' learning outcomes, i.e. improve the informal learning activities. However, in addition to providing insights for improvement of the activities and the activity designers' practice, when integrated into the activity, the assessment can also support engagement of participants in the activity and their knowledge acquisition.

The aim of this document is therefore to guide practitioners in designing and implementing assessments and understand the approach we used to assess both online and in-person activities that can then be used to improve the learning outcomes of their activities (and practice in general). Since recommendations are best given from experience and evidence, we set to test the implementation of assessments that could be used in informal learning activities, with special emphasis on using a diverse set of available approaches. We targeted two contemporary contexts in which informal learning takes place, and in which a particular approach might be especially useful and practical to implement.

We conducted an exploratory study of the feasibility and challenges of assessments in informal education during two types of informal learning activities taking place in 2022. The first one was a special exhibition: evolution happens! and the second was a pair of online workshops 'Evolution

decoded' and 'Assessment decoded'. See '[Short description of the two informal learning activities](#)' for more details about each of them.

In this report, we focus on the theoretical background to, and the practical considerations of designing and implementing assessment in informal learning activities. We more specifically describe the methodology used and the choices made in an exploratory study of two very different non-formal learning formats to show both the importance of assessments to improve practice, and the affordances (for practitioner and participant) of incorporating assessments into the activity design.

Although our focus is on improving the practice, any assessment also represents an opportunity to demonstrate accountability and validate our investment of time, energy, and financial resources to ourselves, to our institution, and to our funding bodies.

Short description of the two activities

Exhibition

The 'evolution happens!' special exhibition (URPP Evolution in Action: From Genomes to Ecosystems, 2021), was displayed at the Zoological Museum of the University of Zurich in 2021 and 2022 (Fig. 1). The exhibition had 7 distinct stations which explored various examples of evolution in action. The main evolutionary concepts the exhibition was designed to reinforce were rapid evolution, evolution does not equate optimisation, and that evolution works on multiple scales (genetic to populations). The exhibition was open to the public whenever the museum was open, and visitors could walk through the exhibition in a self-guided self-directed manner.

Activity features: Self-guided, self-directed, asynchronous, in-person

Figure 1. Photographs from the ‘evolution happens!’ special exhibition. The three stations depicted here focus on the evolution of a) song-loss in Hawaiian crickets, b) body morphology in Caribbean anoles, and c) fur colour in rock pocket mice.

Photo credit: Joelyn de Lima

Workshops

The authors of this document designed and conducted a pair of online workshops ‘Evolution decoded’ and ‘Assessment decoded’, in 2022 (WG3 EuroScitizen, 2022a, 2022b). Evolution decoded was designed to reinforce the main message “Evolution is driven by both random and non-random processes”, and the key message for Assessment decoded was “Assessment should not be an afterthought: use it to improve your practice”.

These synchronous workshops (Fig. 2) were designed for and open to interested educators, scientists and science communicators, especially those focusing on informal evolution education.

Activity features: practitioner-directed, synchronous, online

Figure 2. Logos of the two online synchronous workshops: Evolution decoded and Assessment decoded. They were designed to represent three important evolutionary concepts: Diversity (lower left third), Mutations (right third), and Selection (upper left third)

Logos designed by Sanja Crnjanski, Center for the promotion of science, Serbia

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS IN ASSESSING INFORMAL LEARNING ACTIVITIES

When designing our informal learning activities, and their associated assessments, we chose to start by thinking of the ethical considerations. In academia, and in educational practice, there is a growing demand requiring any and all data collection and research to obtain an ethical approval prior to commencement. While an ethical approval might not be mandatory in all situations, it is good practice to start by thinking of the ethical considerations of the assessment.

Guiding principles

In literature about ethics of assessments, the phrase ‘do no harm’ appears frequently. As it is phrased, it refers to the absence of something, and that something (harm), is very ambiguous. A survey question that seems neutral to one person, could potentially be triggering for another. Therefore, we chose to go one step further and focus instead on two positive ethical guiding principles: Respect and Safety (Fig. 3). Additionally, we considered the ethical considerations from two perspectives: the participants (the ones who would engage in the activity and respond to the assessments), and the practitioners (the ones who would design the activities and assessments, as well as gather the data and analyse it).

Figure 3. Guiding principles in designing ethical assessments of informal learning activities

Ensuring informal learning is respectful:

- Respect the participants' **right to choose**. As far as possible, obtain informed consent.
- Respect the participants' **motivation** for being there. Balance the desire to collect data (and the logistics involved) with their motivations. The assessment should not hinder or negatively affect their experience.
- Respect the participants' **time**. Include only relevant tasks/questions.
- Respect the participants' **privacy**. Maintain confidentiality. As far as possible, do not collect identifying information. Simple demographic information is sufficient in most cases.
- Respect **diversity** in your participants and aim for inclusiveness. If possible, provide opportunities for participants to respond in a language of their choice, or in a mode of their choice (verbal/written).
- Respect the **personal choices, beliefs and social/cultural identities** of the participants. Treat each one with respect.
- Respect the **social and cultural norms** of the practitioner, the participants, and the organisation/institution. A culturally sensitive assessment will increase the quality of the conclusions made and improvements implemented (Frierson et al., 2002).
- Respect the **skills and abilities** of the practitioners. Give them opportunities for professional development in regard to assessments, but also respect their wishes to engage with the assessment (or not).

Ensuring safety in informal education:

- Consider the safety of both the participants and the practitioners. **Physical safety** should not be compromised in the interest of the assessment.
- Also consider the **mental and emotional safety** of the individuals. Vet the assessment tasks to ensure that there are no potential triggering or judgemental items. When asking questions about demographics, avoid binary choices and mandatory questions, and allow participants freedom in disclosing facets of their identity.
- Consider the **ethical implications of the tools** you choose to collect the data. Especially when using online data collection tools, make sure you are aware of their privacy policies including how the data will be used, processed and stored by the service provider.
- Ensure the **safety of the data**. In case identifiable data has been collected (e.g. audio or video recordings), ensure that it is stored and accessed in a manner that maintains confidentiality.

It would be inadvisable to store this data in the cloud, and in many cases, it is illegal to store it outside of your country (e.g. GDPR).

- Ensure that the practitioners are **professionally safe** by getting institutional ethical approvals. Follow the required national and institutional laws and regulations (e.g. GDPR).

For the two studies that we undertook, we obtained ethical approval from two institutions: University of Zurich (museum exhibition), and University of Western Macedonia (online workshops).

Code of Conduct, Trainings and Certifications in Ethics and Human Research

Even when the goal of assessment is improvement of practice, and not research, it is advisable to be aware of and get training in Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practices, especially with respect to working with human subjects.

In Europe, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (All European Academies [ALLEA], 2017), is the recognised document that serves as a framework and guide to consider, and implement responsible and ethical practices. It is available in several European languages.

Many organisations, journals, and countries have now made this a requirement. Practitioners associated with organisations might have access to internal or institutionally funded training and certifications. However, independent practitioners can also avail of e-training programs. The European Network of Research Ethics Committees (<http://www.eurecnet.org/index.html>) has information about national requirements, national ethical approval bodies, as well as ways in which to get training and certifications.

Enacting RRI in EUROPE is a free online course that has been developed by EuroScitizen collaborators (<https://www.en.plan.aau.dk/research+groups/tapar/enacting-rri-in-europe/>). The two modules focus on information about RRI, and RRI in practice. As of the time of publishing this report, the Training and Resources in Research Ethics Evaluation multi-national consortium (<https://elearning.tree.org/>) is offering several free training modules, including one on informed consent. Additional resources and training can also be found on the RRI Tools website (<https://rri-tools.eu/>).

THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE FOR DESIGNING ASSESSMENTS

The reason we collect data through our assessments is to be able to make and support some claims: the participants learnt about mutations, the participants engaged with this exhibit more than the others etc. Before we get into the details and logistics of assessment, it is useful to have a theoretical perspective that we can leverage while designing the assessments.

Goals of Science Education

In the book, *Learning Science in Informal Environments: People, Places, and Pursuits* (National Research Council [NRC], 2009), we are presented with six distinct, but interlinked responses to that question. The authors of the book call them ‘strands’ - but we will refer to them as goals and attempt to underline important considerations that could be addressed in the assessment.

1. “*Developing Interest in Science*” (NRC, 2009)

Most often, people engage with informal learning activities because they ‘want to’ and not because they ‘have to’ - they do it because something about the activity sparks an interest in them. Therefore, an important goal of informal educational activities is to kindle that spark and continue motivating people to engage with further informal learning activities.

The question then becomes: Does the informal learning activity capture the interest of the participant? Whose interest does it capture? And does it then get them further interested in pursuing other informal learning activities, be they on the same scientific topic, or of a similar nature? Research studies have shown that well designed informal learning activities and environments have the potential to attract people who have some prior interest in the topic, increase their levels of interest, and motivate them to relevant socio-scientific action (Falk, Reinhard, et al., 2007; Falk, Storksdieck, et al., 2007; Korn, 2003; NRC, 2009)

2. “*Understanding Science Knowledge*” (NRC, 2009)

Understanding science is not just understanding a set of facts, but understanding how to integrate and link these discrete facts into a coherent idea or theory. How do we build this knowledge? How does this particular informal learning activity help the participant to integrate their prior knowledge about a particular scientific concept and develop their conceptual understanding of the same?

Due to the nature of informal learning activities, it is often not feasible to systematically incorporate every participant's prior knowledge and guide them towards building on it. However, some prior studies have shown that this could be a realistic goal (Borun et al., 1993; Korn, 2003).

3. “*Engaging in Scientific Reasoning*” (NRC, 2009)

Science is not static. New ideas, new discoveries, and most importantly new questions guide the development of science. In today’s world it is particularly important that citizens have the skills to evaluate the information that they are presented with, be able to assess evidence that will help them distinguish relevant facts from ‘fake news’, and make decisions based on sound scientific reasoning. Therefore, an important goal of science education is to teach participants that science progresses through questioning and evaluation, and to help them develop the skills and expertise to do so.

In informal learning activities we can help participants develop these skills by giving them opportunities to interact, ask questions, analyse and visualise data, and make arguments from evidence. One study found that changing the structure and nature of the exhibits encouraged participants to pose more engaging or constructivist types of questions (Humphrey et al., 2017). Other researchers have shown that by intentionally designing informal activities, we can get participants to engage in scientific reasoning skills (Meisner et al., 2007; Stevens & Martell, 2003).

4. “*Reflecting on Science*” (NRC, 2009)

Science is a way of knowing. Over the years, and in light of new evidence, the way scientists think about issues changes. Our understanding of science and the scientific process has evolved and continues to evolve.

In informal science education, we can highlight this change in thinking and understanding by illustrating the changes that have occurred in the field. In evolution for example, we knew about Darwinian evolution, and we knew about Mendelian genetics. But it was only in the 20th century that these two major evolutionary ideas were blended into the modern synthesis. Since then, knowledge about evolutionary biology has continued to develop and scientists are now trying to formulate a unified theory which will include concepts from related fields such as ecology and morphology (Huneman & Walsh, 2017).

5. “*Engaging in Scientific Practice*” (NRC, 2009)

Scientific practices are those sets of processes that allow us to advance science and scientific knowledge. These practices, such as argumentation from evidence, data analysis and visualisation, modelling etc. are commonly used by scientists in their day-to-day lives. One of the goals of informal education then becomes to promote scientific literacy by increasing participants' access to developing these skills, showing them how these skills are relevant to their own daily lives, and encouraging their usage.

Since participants usually engage in informal learning activities by choice, we can say that they are therefore choosing to engage in scientific practices. And some of the ways we can encourage participation is by making our activities relevant to the target populations, and tailoring them to best suit the needs of that population. Additionally, we can make it easier for more people to engage in the activities by paying attention to accessibility, keeping in mind the various challenges faced by our target populations e.g. physical, economic, schedule, spatial etc.

6. “*Identifying with the Scientific Enterprise*” (NRC, 2009)

While most of our participants will not be, or go on to be, scientists, we would like them to include science as a part of their identity. We want them to think of themselves as being ‘a part of’ the scientific community and not ‘apart from’ the scientific community. This scientific identity can take many forms - a person who uses scientific reasoning, a person who keeps up with latest scientific discoveries, a person who contributes to the scientific knowledge, or a person who is interested and keeps learning about science.

Informal learning activities have been shown to be remarkably successful in developing scientific identity by providing participants with diverse opportunities to engage in the scientific process (Schon, 2015). Two very interesting studies showed that after engaging in carefully constructed informal learning activities, a sense of scientific identity increased in populations that traditionally did not self-associate with science (and/or are historically marginalised) such as women and girls (Hughes et al., 2013; Roberts & Hughes, 2022).

What can be assessed in informal learning activities

Learning science in informal settings has a wide range of expected outcomes. These include understanding natural phenomena, evoking positive feelings, developing scientific and learning skills, motivating participants to pursue knowledge further, communicating science's social and individual significance, and being exposed to cutting-edge scientific advancements. Many outcomes fall into two or more interrelated categories based on participants' context and personal characteristics.

Since there are various outcomes in informal educational settings, the assessment should address them accordingly, be valid, specific, and fit with the participant's experience (NRC, 2001a), but not undermine the attractiveness and engaging nature of informal environments.

In the following paragraphs we will explore some outcomes that can be assessed in informal learning activities.

Knowledge

Learning about nature involves focused educational efforts and common everyday experiences (NRC, 2007), and even seemingly minor and inconsequential experiences can lead to learning gains. For example, a single visit to an informal learning environment, such as to a museum or to a nature centre, can lead to knowledge being gained, revised or reinforced (Borun et al., 1993; Guichard, 1995; Korn, 2003; McNamara, 2005).

Although participating in informal learning activities is not expected to lead to huge gains in scientific knowledge, it could lead to gains in the capacity to learn, which in turn would lead to knowledge gains at some point in the future (NRC, 2000). One study looking at the learning gains in visitors to a museum exhibition on life processes, showed high gains in visitors who had very little prior knowledge, and had a lot of interest in the subject (Falk & Storksdieck, 2005).

Designing tests to measure knowledge in informal education is a task that needs a delicate hand. Such assessments should also consider the emotional response of the participant to the assessment, and try to minimise negative emotions, such as feelings of inadequacy or self-disappointment (NRC, 2009).

Knowledge has traditionally been measured by asking participants to self-report (e.g. through interviews, focus groups, and questionnaires). Self-reports can assess how well a person remembers their experience, understands and summarises significant concepts, and demonstrates gains over prior knowledge.

However, some amount of creativity in collecting data that can be used to assess knowledge would go a long way towards enhancing the participant experience. For example, one method that has been used is recording and analysing the content of conversations conducted between visitors as they proceed through an exhibition (Allen, 2002).

Engagement

Informal education settings usually allow learners to engage in the activity by using various resources without being under pressure to perform or demonstrate mastery of a particular topic. In informal education, active engagement is often taken as a proxy for learning, with the assumption being that as participants are actively engaging with the activity (i.e. reading, manipulating the objects, watching the video etc.) they are learning about the topic (NRC, 2009). This 'time on task' has been used to assess the effectiveness of informal learning activities (Serrell, 1997).

Since informal learning activities are not mandatory, and participation in them is voluntary, providing a positive atmosphere and evoking positive emotions is essential to ensure that participants not only continue to engage with the current activity, but also return to engage in future activities (Allen, 2004; Martin, 2004; NRC, 2009). Additionally, creating an environment that is aesthetically pleasing and mentally/cognitively stimulating can increase participants' engagement (Falk, Reinhard, et al., 2007; NRC, 2009).

One common method of assessing engagement is by tracking the attendance. Demographic data on the attendees is useful to determine which participants are choosing to attend the activity (NRC, 2009), and how that maps onto the target audience for the activity. Additionally, using attendance to determine peak engagement timings during the day/week, and using demographics to get a finer grained picture of who comes and when they come, can help appropriately allocate resources such as personnel.

Additionally, such data can help identify potential barriers and accessibility issues (Diamond et al., 2016). For example, if the target demographic is families with very young children, and the attendance shows very few records of such participants, that could indicate that there might be accessibility issues. Perhaps there are no elevators or ramps for parents with strollers to access the activity, or perhaps there is no space for parents to store these strollers. Simple attendance data can potentially highlight issues outside the activity that are hindering engagement.

While collecting attendance data can be challenging (Simpkins et al., 2004), especially for asynchronous and non-guided informal activities, it provides useful information. To some extent, technology can be used to automate data collection, for instance by installing turnstiles or motion detectors.

Engagement in virtual informal learning activities is much easier to assess. Using website or online communication platform analytics it is relatively easy to determine the number of users, 'time on task', numbers of responses, pages visited, the virtual path taken, entrance points from other websites etc. These metrics can all be used to assess the reach and impact of the virtual activity (Rockman et al., 2007).

Motivation

Since informal learning activities are generally not mandatory, people usually engage in them because they are motivated to do so. Being able to control the learning experience (self-directed learning), including the duration and the extent, without there being any adverse consequences to the decisions made is one of the important motivating reasons (NRC, 2009). The degree of, and reasons for, motivation can influence participants' learning by influencing the scope of their engagement with the informal learning activity (Falk & Storksdieck, 2005).

Motivation can be influenced by multiple factors, including general scientific interest, interest in the particular scientific topic highlighted by the activity, interest in introducing children or students to science, interest in engaging with peers, perceptions about their own identities (e.g. identifying as scientific explorers), as well as level of prior formal education (Fahr, 2005; Falk, Reinhard, et al., 2007; NRC, 2009).

A well-designed activity can motivate participants to continue their engagement with science (NRC, 2009), either by participating in similar activities, or by seeking to educate themselves further on the particular topic. Ensuring that informal learning continues to motivate participants, especially young participants, is important because careers in science can result from interest and motivation developed during such activities (Csikszentmihalyi & Hermanson, 1995). Research has demonstrated that students who are motivated to engage in science from an early stage are more likely to pursue and obtain higher scientific education (Tai et al., 2006).

Utility

People often engage with informal education because they gain something from the experience, either with respect to their personal lives or with respect to their professional lives. For example, informal educators might find workshops on new pedagogical techniques useful as a means of professional development. However, in addition to direct utility, participation in such activities could also have indirect professional utility benefits, such as enhancing transversal skills (e.g. team work) (Fahr, 2005). People also choose to participate in informal learning activities because the utility they perceive is related to their personal love of learning (Fahr, 2005). The utility of an informal

activity will not be uniform for all the participants and will be linked to their professional and personal interests. These interests could also include socialising, networking, or building a community of shared interests.

The utility of informal learning also extends to the society at large, including to the labour market and the economy (NRC, 2009; Rüber & Bol, 2017). This utility is most salient in the light of society today which is facing multiple environmental, social disasters and crises. Community-based informal education can be leveraged to equip societies to deal with and mitigate such disasters (Dufty, 2020; Feng et al., 2017). Additionally, skills that are highly relevant to building a scientifically literate society, including being able to reason from evidence and make informed decisions, are also often developed by participating in informal learning activities (NRC, 2009)

Attitudes, feelings, behaviours

By engaging in science education, people develop more than knowledge and skills - they also develop attitudes, and behaviours that are inherent in science and the pursuit of science. While these can be mere by-products of the learning objectives (which might focus on knowledge or skills), developing certain attitudes and behaviours can also be the explicit focus of the informal learning activity. Additionally, attitudes and behaviours can also be communicated via the choices made in the instructional style, the supporting material used, and by being modelled by the facilitators.

Research has shown that visitors' attitudes towards conservation, as well as their intentions to engage in conservation-related behaviours, improved after a visit to an exhibition on conservation, even though the visits were self-guided (Dierking et al., 2004; Falk & Adelman, 2003).

Researchers have also shown that informal education can elicit strong emotions in participants (Myers Jr. et al., 2004), and that these emotions are important in enhancing the learning process (Sherman et al., 2022) and in stimulating desirable behaviours (Clayton et al., 2009; Godinez & Fernandez, 2019; Staus & Falk, 2017). Informal education thus has an important goal of connecting the cognitive and affective domains, by eliciting an emotional response from the participants (NRC, 2009). Additionally, making the experience enjoyable, creates a connection between fun or entertainment, and science for the participants. Such connections make the main ideas more relatable and relevant to the participants. Increasing the potential emotional responses (awe, surprise, amusement, sense of connection etc.) can help increase the reach and retention of the activity (NRC, 2009).

Acceptance

When it comes to evolution in particular, one attitude that is of great relevance is '**Acceptance of Evolution**'. Acceptance of evolution is affected by and correlated with multiple other aspects of a person's identity, including level of knowledge about evolution, understanding of the nature of science, science literacy, religious belief, etc (Dunk et al., 2017; Ha et al., 2012; Heddy & Nadelson, 2012).

Well-designed informal learning activities can help increase evolutionary acceptance (Groß et al., 2019). However, it has also been shown that participants who choose to engage in informal education about evolution already have positive attitudes towards evolution, and are generally more accepting of evolution than the general public (Barone & Buntin, 2014).

Conceptual Framework for assessing knowledge

As we have seen in the previous sections, there are several goals of a science education, and there are several aspects of informal scientific learning activities that we could assess. However, a common goal that most educators focus on is 'Scientific Knowledge'. When it comes to assessing knowledge, the important questions are: What is it that the participants should learn from engaging in this activity? And how can the data support claims about their learning gains? This process – in which we collect evidence, and then use it to support some conclusions – is called *reasoning from evidence* (NRC, 2001b). Therefore, it becomes very important that the evidence we collect is both valid and reliable.

A framework designed to enhance the reliability and validity of assessments was proposed in the report 'Knowing What Students Know: The Science and Design of Educational Assessment' (NRC, 2001a, p 44). The highlight of this framework is the "*central role of a model of cognition and learning*" and an "*interpretation model that fits the model of cognition and learning*". Keeping this in mind they proposed the Assessment triangle (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. The Assessment Triangle. It describes 3 interdependent elements to take into consideration when assessing gained knowledge (NRC, 2001a, p 44)

In this framework, assessment has three unique, but interlinked and interdependent, entities.

Cognition

This is the part that is most guided by cognitive theories and prior research. Simply put, it answers the questions ‘what is the participant expected to know?’ and ‘what are some of the theories that guide your knowledge of what the participant knows?’. This report will walk through one cognitive theory that could be used to think about evolution education and assessment in the section [Cognitive Model for Evolution Education](#).

Additionally, while having some theoretical grounding would be optimal, it is also important to ground the assessments on evidence, such as from prior experience. E.g. a pre-school educator would not ask a 5-year-old student to explain the intricacies of the evolutionary process, because they know from experience that a child in that age group does not have the conceptual knowledge.

Ideally, the cognition part of the assessment triangle will be guided by both perspectives: the theoretical, and the experiential.

Observation

Designing the assessment tools is linked to the two other corners of the assessment triangle, the cognitive theories that underpin the questions, as well as the nature of the interpretations that are

to be made. What is expected from the participants, what claim is to be made, and what data will best link those two together.

Assessments should be designed taking into careful consideration the affordances and limitations of each particular situation (time, money, technology etc.). E.g. interviews can give really high-quality data, but they are a tremendous time investment from the perspectives of both the participants and the practitioners, and might not be worth it for a short 5-min activity.

Another factor to be considered at this stage is the purpose of the assessment. If it is to show learning gains, the participants should be able to demonstrate their learning. If the purpose is to show the difference in engagement between two demographic populations, the assessment should ensure that demographic details are collected.

The assessment should be tailored as far as possible to the particular activity, the audience and the purpose of the assessment.

Interpretation

Once the assessment data has been collected, it has to be analysed, interpreted and used to generate claims (conclusions) that are not only supported by the collected evidence, but are also guided by cognitive theories. Before analysing the data and interpreting it, it is advisable to take a step back and consider some of the assumptions that might influence the conclusions.

Some potential questions that might influence interpretation are:

- How will the data be analysed? (what are the built-in assumptions made by the method of analysis chosen?)
- How much data do you have, and does it have the power to make any significant claims?
- How can it best be visualised to help facilitate interpretation?
- What was the primary goal of assessment? And could the secondary goals have introduced any bias? For example - if the primary goal was to assess knowledge, but the secondary goal was to demonstrate that the money invested has been well spent - there might be a potential conflict there.

Cognitive Model for Evolution Education

As we aim to address assessment of evolution-themed informal learning activities, it is essential to consider which concepts play a significant role in cognitive understanding of evolution. In their paper, Opfer et al. (2012), proposed a cognitive model for evolution education. This model is based on 4 main themes:

1. **“Theme 1: In the Development of Expertise, Core Concepts Facilitate Long-Term Recall.”** (Opfer et al., 2012)

For participants to be able to recall information after participating in an activity, this information has to be encoded into their long-term memory. This encoding is enhanced if the information is about or relating to the core concepts of the topic under consideration.

With respect to evolution, the general consensus is that the core concepts are variation, heritability and differential survival – which can then be used to explain natural selection (Moharreri et al., 2014; Opfer et al., 2012; Papale et al., 2020).

2. **“Theme 2: In the Development of Expertise, Causally-Central Information is Weighted More Heavily in Student's Explanations.”** (Opfer et al., 2012)

The level of participants' expertise in the subject, and the level of their conceptual understanding, can be determined by the nature of the relationships in their explanations. Participants who have understood the individual core concepts, as well as their relationships to each other and evolutionary theory, will generate explanations that illustrate these causal links in a scientifically plausible manner. For example, they will talk of mutations that *cause* variation which in turn *causes* differential survival.

Participants could also talk of causes that are not supported by science, and this would highlight the fact that they do not have a conceptual understanding of evolution. Explanations that have non-scientific causes such as teleology (giraffes grew long necks because they had to reach higher branches), agency (human stood upright because he wanted to), essentialism (monkeys have tails because they are animals), intelligent design (plants were created by God), demonstrate that the participant still has some naïve ideas about evolution and the evolutionary process.

3. **“Theme 3: Throughout the Development of Expertise, Normative, and Naive Ideas Continue to Co-Exist.”** (Opfer et al., 2012)

Research has consistently shown, that in a topic as difficult, non-intuitive, and perhaps controversial as evolution, scientifically accurate knowledge and ideas often coexist with naïve ideas and non-normative reasoning (Bishop & Anderson, 1990; Bray Speth et al., 2009; Catley & Novick, 2009; Nehm & Reilly, 2007).

4. **“Theme 4: In the Development of Expertise, Knowledge Becomes More Abstract and Less Specific to the Learning Situation.”** (Opfer et al., 2012)

Participants with weaker conceptual understanding of evolution will tend to focus more on the superficial (and sometimes unimportant) features of the questions. Various researchers have shown that people respond differently to questions that test the same conceptual knowledge, but are phrased slightly differently (de Lima, 2021; Nehm & Ha, 2011; Nehm & Schonfeld, 2008).

However, as expertise develops, participants tend to narrow in on the deeper and more conceptual aspects of the questions. Additionally, their explanations also become more abstract, and they talk about the conceptual ideas, rather than the specific scenarios in the questions.

The cognitive model proposed above is one possible model that can be used to scaffold the cognition part of the assessment triangle. The authors of this report chose to describe it because it was designed for evolution education.

ASSESSMENT DESIGN FOR INFORMAL LEARNING ACTIVITIES

Customising Assessment Design

Assessing informal learning activities is not easy. There are various challenges – including technical, logistical and issues relating to expertise in designing and implementing assessments. These, and many other difficulties, are well known to the educational community and have been documented in multiple studies (NRC, 2009).

Just as informal learning activities are diverse in type, duration, audience etc, assessments of informal learning activities are also diverse. There is no one-size-fits-all assessment. The assessment design should then fit the needs of the specific situation.

While there are always examples and models of assessments that practitioners can use, they will be most useful if they are then modified and customised to suit the need of the moment. Some of the factors that practitioners will have to consider are:

- What are your aims?

This should be the first question asked. What is the purpose of conducting this assessment? Reasons could range from improving practice to demonstrating accountability. Explicitly stating the aim of the assessment will facilitate every subsequent step in the assessment process (Diamond et al., 2016)

- What are your affordances?

Every practitioner will have some affordances at their disposal as well as some limitations. Having an idea of what is, or is not, possible/achievable is key in planning a successful assessment. For example, it might not be logistically possible to have participants fill out questionnaires (that eliminates a potential data collection method) or one of the collaborators might be proficient in qualitative data analysis (that would make collecting and analysing such data feasible). Other factors to be considered are resources including personnel, time, available equipment, and budget.

- How do you measure success?

This is a very important question, and can often be a sticking point. How do you measure success? Is the benchmark the same for everyone or does that benchmark change with the demographics?

- Who is the audience?

Once the assessment is completed, who will see the results/report? Is it meant only for the practitioner? Will it be shared with colleagues? Presented to the funding body? Disseminated at a meeting or conference? Or published in a research journal?

- Which concepts to assess?

In a museum and at a workshop, every participant has the opportunity to learn the same concepts. But whereas at a workshop, every participant engages in the same activities, in a museum, participants can choose to go to all the exhibits or none. Which concepts should then be assessed? It is also a good idea to think about the concepts that this assessment will not focus on.

- Group data or Individual data?

People usually go to museums in a group, and when there, talk to each other about the exhibits. Learning therefore takes a collective dimension. Should the assessment then be one questionnaire that the group fills out? Or one questionnaire per individual?

- Control group

In informal education there is generally no control group. But an additional perspective might be useful for comparison. The question then becomes what/who to compare to? The same activity at different time points, different iterations of the same activity? Other activities? Other locations? Other similar studies?

Our exploratory study: Comparing two approaches to assessment design

The authors of this report designed and implemented assessments for two informal learning activities. Table 1 illustrates the differences in the approaches used in both these situations.

Table 1. A comparison of the differences in the assessment design process between two informal learning activities.

	Exhibition	Workshops
Brief description	In-person asynchronous activity	Online synchronous activity
Timing of assessment design	After the activity was designed. The assessment design was separated from the design of the activity.	In synchrony with designing the activity. The assessment was designed along with the activity.
Assessment design	The assessment instruments (questionnaires, observation forms) were designed for this activity. The questions had theoretical grounding, but were developed for this particular activity.	The assessments were mostly based on existing instruments. Questions from published instruments were chosen and modified to suit the needs of the activity.
Assessment designer experience	The activity and the assessment were designed by two separate teams. There was no interaction between the two teams.	The same team designed both the activity and the assessments and had intimate knowledge of all the facets of the activity.
Participant experience	There was no effect of the assessment on the participant experience. Data was collected by observing them at a distance, and by providing a questionnaire after they had finished engaging with the exhibition.	Since the assessments were an integral part of the activity, they affected the participant experience. Knowledge questions during the workshop served as checkpoints for the participants as well as the practitioners.

While both these assessments integrated all the three aspects of the assessment triangle (Fig. 4), they differed in the approaches they took. Each activity had its own affordances and limitations, and the authors worked within the constraints to design and implement assessments to the best of their abilities.

Timing of the Assessment (Implementation)

In the guide, ‘Developing non-formal learning activities focused on increasing evolutionary knowledge and scientific literacy’ (de Lima et al., 2023), the authors present a comprehensive overview of informal learning activities. While not repeating the information, the authors of this report would like to present a simplified version of the timeline for assessments that practitioners can use.

In general, assessment is possible at three timepoints: before the participants engage in the activity, while they are engaged, and after they finish engaging in the activity. Each of the three timepoints provides unique affordances with respect to what can be assessed, and therefore what type of claims that data can be used to support (Fig. 5)

Figure 5. Potential timings of implementing assessments in informal learning activities

Assessing before the activity

Assessments done before the participants can engage with the activity (i.e. before they enter the exhibit hall, or before the workshop starts) can help the practitioner set up a baseline of the participants' knowledge/attitude/belief and their expectations (Diamond et al., 2016). This can then be used to compare with a similar assessment done at the end of the activity to assess the learning gains.

Additionally, knowing participants' prior knowledge and expectations can in some circumstances allow the practitioner to tailor the activity (e.g. introduce or drop certain activities in the workshop) to best suit the needs of the current participant(s).

Assessing during the activity

This can be compared to formative feedback that happens in formal education scenarios. Assessments during the activity can serve as checkpoints for both the participants and the practitioner.

These assessments can be used to make immediate changes in an ongoing activity (e.g. if most of the participants choose a particular evolutionary misconception, the practitioner can pause the activity and address that misconception), or minor tweaks in the next activity (the practitioner can intentionally address the misconception before asking the question).

In asynchronous activities, such as museum exhibits, such assessments can help identify and fix logistical and structural issues (e.g. problems with the interactive exhibits, QR codes, lighting issues etc) (Diamond et al., 2016).

Assessing after the activity

Carefully designed assessments will allow the practitioner to measure learning gains, even if there was no opportunity to conduct an assessment prior to beginning the activity. Alternatively, the responses from activity participants could be compared with those given by people (similar demographics) who did not participate in the activity (Diamond et al., 2016).

In addition to learning gains, impact can be measured by getting an overall picture of the number and demographics of the participants, and comparing that with initial targets. The data obtained can also be used as evidence in planning for improvements both for future editions of the same activity, or other related activities.

Our exploratory study: Comparing two approaches to timing of assessments

The authors of this report designed and implemented assessments for two informal learning activities. Figure 6 illustrates the different times at which various aspects were assessed for these two activities.

Figure 6. Different outcomes were assessed before, during and after the activity, in the a) Exhibition and b) Workshops

CONSTRUCTING ASSESSMENTS FOR EVOLUTION-THEMED INFORMAL LEARNING ACTIVITIES

Constructing assessments for informal learning activities is a multivariate process which should be guided by the goal of the assessment and the aspects to be assessed (see [What can be assessed in informal learning activities](#)). As mentioned before ([Customising Assessment Design](#)), customisation is key in assessment design, thus should also run through assessment construction around the pre-set goals on aspects such as knowledge, motivation, engagement or other.

Those aspects will direct the type of the assessment, as well as all the adaptations to be made according to the type of informal-learning activity, audience, etc. Some of the factors that educators and practitioners will have to consider when assessing these aspects are summarised below:

How to assess knowledge (*What did they learn?*)

The main objective for most informal activities is for the participants to gain knowledge about a subject. The first step therefore, should be to articulate a specific and clear learning goal. Only then the appropriate assessment tools to measure knowledge acquisition can be constructed, either benefitting from existing instruments measuring knowledge on the subject or by designing new ones. There are several published tools or sets of questions, such as concept inventories or questionnaires available, which when used in research should always be tested for reliability and validity. However, in informal educational settings, as long as the aim is not conducting research but improving the practice, those tools can be modified to suit the needs of the practitioners. For a list of **evolution-based concept inventories**, refer to Table 2 in the paper 'Concept inventories as a resource for teaching evolution' (Furrow & Hsu, 2019). Some other tools that can be used to assess evolutionary knowledge are CINS (Anderson et al., 2002), EEQ (Beniermann et al., 2021), CANS (Kalinowski et al., 2016), BCI (Garvin-Doxas & Klymkowsky, 2008; Klymkowsky et al., 2010), the genetic drift inventory (Price et al., 2014), ACORNS (Nehm et al., 2012), and KAEVO (Kuschmierz et al., 2020).

When assessing evolutionary knowledge, questions can be designed to determine what knowledge the participant has/has gained, but also to determine prior or persistent **evolutionary misconceptions**. There are two main categories of questions that can be used, i.e. objective and subjective questions; their distinction depends respectively on the provision or not of response options. On one hand, formats like multiple-choice and 'true or false' provide the opportunity to test participants' knowledge and pinpoint any misconceptions or false ideas they may hold, by providing a set of correct and false responses. On the other hand, subjective questions are usually open-

ended questions in a questionnaire or an interview, where participants are asked to demonstrate their knowledge on a subject without limitations or guidance that provided answers could give.

Our exploratory study: Comparing two approaches to assessing evolutionary knowledge

The authors of this report used two different strategies to assess evolutionary knowledge (Fig. 7). They differed in the way the data collection instrument was designed (Design), the methods used to collect the data (Data) and the time at which the data was collected (Timing). While designing the questions to assess knowledge, the authors used existing instruments (See: Anderson et al., 2002; Beniermann et al., 2021; Kalinowski et al., 2016; Nehm et al., 2012).

Figure 7. Comparing two different strategies to assess participants' conceptual knowledge for an exhibition and an online workshop

How to assess engagement (*What did they do?*)

Engagement is vastly dependent on the audience and the type of informal activity, thus should always be tailored accordingly. **Demographics** (age, country of origin, profession, educational background, etc.) of participants, usually are used to illustrate the reach of the activity and determine whether the reach included the target audience. To obtain such data, and avoid making any assumptions about the demographics of the participants, some efficient methods are polling the participants through application forms, questionnaires, or by asking them questions in person. Metrics of assessing participant engagement include counting the **number of participants**, the **time of their engagement** with specific tasks (i.e. museum exhibit in an exhibition), the **number of tasks completed** (i.e. in a workshop) or the **willingness to engage with future activities**.

Our exploratory study: Comparing two approaches to assessing in-activity engagement and determining the demographics

The authors of this report assessed engagement by measuring in-activity engagement (Fig. 8) and by asking questions about demographics (Fig. 9). Strategies to assess engagement differed in the way the data collection instrument was designed (Design), the methods used to collect the data (Data) and the time at which the data was collected (Timing).

Figure 8. Comparing two different strategies to assess participants' in-activity engagement for an exhibition and an online workshop

Figure 9. Comparing two different strategies to determine the demographics of the participants for an exhibition and an online workshop

How to assess motivation (*Why did they do it?*)

Assessing participants' motivation relies on the subjective view of participants themselves. And the best way to discover the reason they are/were **interested in being part of the activity** is asking them. That can be achieved through questions integrated in application forms, questionnaires or interviews.

Our exploratory study: Comparing two approaches to assessing participants' motivation

The authors of this report assessed participants' motivation by asking them to respond to a subjective question in both informal activities (same Design) (Fig. 10). However, the methods used to collect the data (Data) and the time at which the data was collected (Timing) differed for the two activities.

Figure 10. Comparing two different strategies to determine the motivation of the participants for an exhibition and an online workshop

How to assess utility (Was it useful for you?)

Assessing utility can take multiple perspectives, including the perspective of the participant and the perspective of the society/community. From the participant's perspective one way to assess utility would be to ask them **how useful the activity was in terms of their professional and personal lives**. These questions can be qualitative (Describe how this activity was useful to you) or quantitative (On a scale of 0 - 10, how useful was participating activity for your professional life). Having some demographic information about the participants will allow the practitioner to link utility with specific professions, age groups etc. Recordings of the activity, and products of the activity can be analysed to determine the diversity and level of skills developed.

From a societal perspective, utility can be assessed by mapping the learning goals of the activity onto the **goals of strategic plans** and needs assessments. This information can then be used to demonstrate utility and target the marketing of the activity.

Our exploratory study: Comparing two approaches to assessing the utility

The authors of this report only assessed the utility of the workshops (Fig. 11), by posing questions to a subset of the participants during follow-up interviews.

Figure 11. Utility was assessed only for a subset of the workshop participants, and not for the exhibition

How to assess attitudes (*What do they think/believe in?*)

Attitudes and personal opinions or beliefs greatly influence learning and understanding of participants, so assessing them provides an insight of the informal learning activities' impact. Attitudes can be assessed by asking participants to rate their agreement to statements that illustrate multiple dimensions of the issue. It is advisable to have multiple statements that test each dimension to improve the reliability of the results.

Knowing the attitudes of participants on certain subjects may enhance our interpretation of assessment results, as well as the extent practitioners can adapt the activities to ameliorate the impact they can have.

There are multiple surveys and instruments available that can be used to assess **attitudes towards science** (see: Chen, 2006; Guzey et al., 2014; Liang et al., 2006; Moore & Foy, 1997). For a compilation of multiple instruments see Lovelace & Brickman, (2013).

With respect to evolution, practitioners might be interested in measuring **evolutionary acceptance**, and there are multiple existing instruments that can be used. Some of them are GAENE (Smith et al., 2016), SECM (Sbeglia & Nehm, 2020), and I-SEA (Nadelson & Southerland, 2012).

Our exploratory study: Comparing two approaches to assessing attitudes towards science

The authors of this report only assessed attitudes towards science in the participants who came to the exhibition (Fig. 12). This was done using modified Likert style questions based on Liang et al. (2006).

Figure 12. Attitudes towards science were only assessed in the exhibition.

REFLECTIONS, AND SOME LESSONS LEARNT

A critical aspect of using assessments to improve practice is engaging in reflection (Archer et al., 2022; Patrick, 2017) When talking about practitioners reflecting on their practice, Donald Schön in their seminal work *The Reflective Practitioner: How Professionals Think in Action* says “***The situation talks back, the practitioner listens, and as he appreciates what he hears, he reframes the situation once again.***” (Schön, 1992).

And so, we the authors of this report, will take a moment to reflect on this exploratory study. We will reflect on our experiences designing and implementing the assessments in these two distinct scenarios. To do so, we will use the themes that we explored in this report.

Ethics

We placed a high premium on ensuring high ethical standards while conducting this study. As we had collaborators associated with research universities, we were able to obtain ethical approvals with minor effort. However, since this might not be possible for many practitioners in informal education, we have indicated ways in which practitioners could get information, training and certifications.

Timing of assessment design

Designing assessments for the online workshops was a rather easy task, since the activity and assessments were being designed simultaneously and by the same people. This allowed us to use the assessments to tailor the activity and vice versa. We believe the participants' experience was more streamlined, since they considered the assessments to be an integral part of the workshop. A consequential benefit for us was that we got data from a majority of the participants.

On the contrary, designing assessments for an exhibition after it had already launched, and without input from the exhibition designers, was a little more challenging, but doable just the same. From the participants' viewpoint, the assessment was ‘a part from’ their visit to the exhibition, a questionnaire they filled in after they exited the exhibition hall. Since the assessment was not integrated with their visit, we were only able to get data from a fraction of the visitors.

Assessing various outcomes

Of the various outcomes that we targeted, assessing knowledge was the easiest, both in terms of designing the questions, and analysing the data. This might be because several of us are formal educators and are used to assessing knowledge in the classroom. However, we think that practitioners will also find it easy to assess evolutionary knowledge, especially since there are so many published instruments that they could use or adapt to suit their particular needs. Additionally, since practitioners design activities with specific learning goals in mind, this will allow them to then easily tailor the assessment to find out if the learning goal was achieved.

Assessing engagement in online activities was very straightforward, since many dimensions of engagement are directly tabulated by the online tools we used. Assessing engagement in the in-person activity was a much more difficult task, and needed a lot of man-power and man-hours. Therefore, while practitioners can make assessing engagement a default in online activities, they should consider the trade-off in terms of what information they could gain (and the affordances of having that data) weighed against the time and effort that would need to be invested.

Assessing motivation, utility, and attitudes is a bit more challenging and will be useful if the practitioner can link that information to some demographic data. It would also be important to first reflect on which question would be interesting to answer (such as “Does motivation depend on the age of the participant?” or “Does the attitude toward evolution depend on gender?”) and then consider whether gathering relevant and sufficient data is feasible.

Overall reflections and intentions

When designing future informal learning activities, we will definitely ensure that assessment is not just a part of the activity but is a part of the assessment design. However, we will reframe some of our approaches based on our post-study reflections. Table 2 summarises some of the challenges and affordances we experienced. When considering assessment, practitioners may want to use the findings of our exploratory study to select the assessment methodology for their informal learning activities. Please note that this is our subjective opinion based on our experiences designing assessments in this exploratory study.

Table 2. Challenges and affordances of various aspects of assessment design.

	Easier to implement	Harder to implement
Ethical considerations	Obtaining institutional ethical approval for data collection if working with researchers	Obtaining institutional ethical approval for data collection if researchers are not involved
Timing of assessment design	Integrating assessment design with activity design	Designing the assessment after the design of the activity
Timing of the assessment	For asynchronous activities: Assessment during the activity For synchronous activities: Assessment at the beginning and the end of the activity	For asynchronous activities: Assessment at the beginning and the end of the activity For synchronous activities: Assessment during the activity
Assessing outcomes	Assessing knowledge and engagement	Assessing motivation, utility and attitudes

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PRACTITIONERS

In this practitioners' guide to assessing online and offline informal learning activities to promote understanding of evolution we have presented the theoretical background on what the assessment is and why it is important. Additionally, we have showcased what can be assessed, how an assessment can be designed, and how it can be tailored to suit diverse needs. This section will focus on a set of recommendations that practitioners should have in their mind when starting to design their next informal educational activities.

Assessment matters! Therefore, our biggest recommendation for practitioners is to **build assessments into the activities**. Plan for what you want to assess, when you want to assess it, and how you want to assess it, when you are designing the activity. In this way it will be integrated organically into the activity design and will not become an afterthought. When designing the assessment instead of (or in addition to) assessing satisfaction the assessment can focus on multiple other dimensions such as knowledge, motivation, engagement and participants' attitudes.

Rather than developing the assessments from scratch, **take the advantage of pre-existing instruments** that have been developed for assessing similar concepts and dimensions. If the activity is based on evolution there is a list of resources provided in the '[Constructing assessments for evolution-themed informal learning activities](#)' section of this document. An important requirement of informal activities is to provide enjoyment to, and evoke positive emotions in the participants. Because of this, you need to **balance the learning goals and the participants' learning experience with your need to collect assessment data** so as to improve the assessment/learning outcomes. Being focused, effective, and concrete about your assessment plans will allow you to utilise your resources (including your and your participants' time) efficiently.

Sometimes, things do not go smoothly during the activity. There might not be enough time needed to complete everything that you have planned. That is why you need to be prepared and to **have a contingency plan**.

Once you have finished implementing the assessments, take some time to **reflect on your findings**. Use some of the ideas from the [Interpretation](#) section. Since the ultimate goal of assessments is to help you improve your practice, this data can provide you with useful information on how to improve the current activity to meet your goals, and also to help you improve your practice in general.

And finally, **disseminate your findings**. Other informal education practitioners will benefit from your experience. What you learned in your situation will help other practitioners avoid pitfalls, and improve the activities they are designing. As a global community, we can collectively work towards improving informal education through assessment.

Assessment matters! And you can do it!

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